

GAMES, SONGS AND POEMS IN GERMAN LESSONS

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Abstract.

In article was discussed music, activities, and poems based on the lesson theme. Their characteristics are critical in developing students' knowledge based on their abilities. The most crucial rule for the game is that they thoroughly comprehend the students and the game's regulations. The game must not be very complicated; it must be enjoyable, interesting, and inspiring, and it must provide the opportunity to compete without penalty.

Key words.

Games, teacher, lesson, pupils, German, team work, teaching process, interaction, motivation, songs, poems, interesting

"Language strengthening is always good for a child and developing one language can never harm another."

Tsvetelina Ortega

The games.

Another suitable method for enlivening the lesson is the incorporation of games. With the help of the games, the pupils not only practice a specific subject, but they also improve their communication and expression skills and expand their vocabulary. The games should also motivate the pupils and be fun for them. They learn how to win and lose and how to work together when they play a game as a team.

The rules for incorporating games into lessons.

The most important rule for the game is that they understand the pupils well and the Understand the rules of the game. The game must not be too complicated, it must be fun, exciting, motivating and offer the opportunity to compete without penalties. There may also be a reward after the game (e.g. an A for the winner, a plus for the pupil who came second, and if the pupils got three pluses, he also gets an A) Never should the teacher humiliate the pupils for a bad result. Before playing, the teacher should check whether the students understand the game well

and master the required vocabulary. He also determines a place for the game. He does not have to tell the pupils in advance what they are practicing using the game. You should notice this within the game itself. The teacher does not play with the pupils as he could influence the outcome. After the game, the evaluation should follow. The games can be integrated into the lessons according to need. At the beginning of the lesson for the repetition of the previous lesson material, in the middle of the lesson for practicing the topic just learned or for a change of pace lessons when the students are tired. The teacher can also insert a game at the end of the lesson if he still has time.

Interesting games suitable for German lessons

1) Who puts together as many words as possible from the concrete letters? In this game, pupils can work alone or in groups. We give the pupils a series of letters - e.g. EGIRHSELMN. This series of letters can be reduced or expanded with more letters. The pupils put together as many words as possible, using only the given letters and only as often as they are contained in the task. All the words that the pupils put together should be written on the blackboard by the teacher. Everyone writes down the words they didn't put together in their vocabulary notebook, which allows each pupils to expand their vocabulary. The words you get from the given letters can be put together are e.g. Eis, Regie, Esel, lesen, es, sie, er, Ei, ein, eine, eins, mein, meine, Mehl, Reis, Regen, gern, Lege, Sieger, Seher, sehen, Helm, mir, ihm, ihn, Segel, segeln, Segen, reisen, Riege, Riegel, Reihe, reihen, rieseln, mies, Gier, sehr, Hirn, Igel etc. Another row of letters can be e.g. NEHRLNRPENAZ - the combined letters form words like e.g. Herz, zehn, er, Reh, lernen, Ranzen, rennen, Lehrer, Narr, Lehre, lehren, lernen, Zehe, Henne, Haar, Haare, planen, Panne, lehnen, Paar, Paare, Herr, Zahl, zahlen, Zahn, Plan and many more.

2) The word snake The teacher writes the first word on the blackboard e.g. dandelion. The students form a word snake. The word " Löwenzahn " ends in "zahn" so pupils need to come up with a word that starts with " Zahn ", e.g. Zahnbürste. Sometimes the pupils can't think of another word. Therefore the teacher takes only part of the Word "Bürste " - e.g. "ste" and the pupils continue: Sternhimmel - Himmelskriege - Kriegerstand - Standort - Ortsgespräch etc.

3) We practice the numbers This game is simpler, it is suitable for warming up at the beginning of the lesson or as a change when the students are tired. In this game, the pupils can of course remain seated in their desks, but it is better if they sit or stand in a circle. The teacher needs only one tool, and that is a small soft ball. A pupils (or the teacher) begins, throws the ball to another pupils and says any three-digit number, e.g. three hundred and forty-eight (348). The pupils who catches the

ball must again say a three-digit number beginning with the last digit the previous number ended with. In our example, this is the number eight. The pupils keep going. If the number "zero" appears at the end, e.g. four hundred and twenty, the next student thinks up a new random number. However, it is better to establish a rule that the number "zero" must not appear at the end. Who knows nothing or says a wrong number is dropped. In this game, the students practice not only the numbers up to a thousand, but also memory and concentration.

4) What do we have in common? Pupils form groups of three, four or five (depending on the number of students in the class). In groups, pupils need to identify what they have in common. For example: We all have an animal at home. Nobody has a brother. Each of us likes bread with butter and jam. We are all over 170 meters tall and 17 years old. None of us can play the piano. Our whole group lives in Usbekistan. Each of us has already visited Samarkand. The goal is to find as many common features as possible. The game is more difficult the more members the group has. With the help of this game, the pupils primarily practice conversation, vocabulary, and the formation of statements and interrogative sentences. This game helps to improve the climate of the school class.

5) Ich heie ... Each pupils writes their name down. For each letter in his name, he must write any property that characterizes him. For example, the student named "PETER" thinks up these words: P for pnktlich, E for ehrlich, T for treu, E for empathisch, R for ruhig. This game helps pupils get to know each other better. They get a new vocabulary or practice working with the dictionary.

6) Who am I? One pupils represents a selected well-known German-speaking person. The other pupils can only ask him the questions that can only be answered with "yes" or "no". You have to guess who he is as quickly as possible.

7) Who stops the ABC? The teacher can play with the pupils a classic popular game with different modifications. For example, the categories can look like this: a) a German city, a German proper name, a river, an animal, a plant, a concrete thing, an abstract thing, a well-known personality from a German-speaking country; b) a noun, verb, adjective, preposition/conjunction One pupils quietly recites the ABC to himself, another says "stop". The student work with the letter the first student just finished on. You have to think of a word in each category.

8) Who can think of as many words with the letter ... as possible? The students have to think of as many words as possible that start with a certain start letters, make them up. They can then use these words to form sentences. pupils can work alone or in groups.

9) Who has as many words as possible in the sentence? Each student or the groups complete a sentence that the teacher sends to the chalkboard wrote. The goal is to form the longest sentence. For example: Some people say The condition is not to add another main clause or subordinate clause. The pupils are only allowed to extend the main clause "Some people say." with one subordinate clause, der can contain any number of clauses.

10) Word tennis Only two students can play this game at a time. A pupils names the participle of any strong verb. The second student must use this form of the verb in the sentence. The first pupils then names the infinitive and also the Czech translation of this participle. Then the second student thinks up another participle and the word tennis game can begin again.

German songs

There are many important reasons for using songs in German lessons: songs are, above all, authentic texts, you can use them to train the four skills, they make pronunciation easier and they impart knowledge of the country. You can use songs for almost every lesson or textbook unit, as they allow a creative and motivating use of the German language and address emotional and communicative skills. With songs and music, learners' communicative and social skills improve; They are encouraged to perform and have the opportunity to compensate for lack of concentration, to reduce inhibitions and fears in the classroom and to break up the monotony of the classroom It is very difficult to select suitable songs for middle school students. Most pupils feel shy and do not want to sing in front of other classmates. Or we don't meet their taste in music. The teacher can choose some songs themselves or the students can create their own say suggestions. Pupils can search the internet for popular songs themselves by German-speaking singers or music groups (with lyrics and music) and other students then learn to sing these songs as well. However, some students do not want to sing. This is not a problem. The teacher can only listen to the songs with them and then continue to work with the lyrics of the song.

Depending on the objective, the following teaching activities can be carried out with the songs:

If you want to practice listening comprehension, you can:

- Fill in the gaps in the text
- Put lines/sections in order, put them in the right order
- Find out rhymes
- Cross out wrong words
- Correct wrong lyrics of the song

- write down what you understand
- list the number of times a word/sentence/rhyme occurs
- Identify keywords or pick out keywords
- Number/arrange words from a line

If you want to practice reading comprehension, you can:

- have the song reconstructed. (puzzle/lines)
- create a glossary of vocabulary
- read the song step by step and form hypotheses about the history, motives etc. or above all the further progress (speculation / anticipation)
- Create search questions / quiz questions / assignment questions / control questions about the song and have them answered
- Fill in / complete the summary / questionnaire / grid / table for the lyrics
- Match picture / question / answer / music text
- Find / collect / read information / lyrics about performers / plot / people / situation / theme / action of the song

If you want to use some games you can:

- Write lines or sections of a song on large slips of paper and give them to learners to put together in the correct order. Either have the lines or sections lay down on the floor while listening, or properly line up/dance into a line or dance line.
- Act out mini-plays / mini-dialogues / role-plays / sketches with the lyrics

Working with songs primarily increases the motivation of our mostly young learners, appeals to their feelings and also to their bodies.

German poems

Poems are ideal for meaningful speech and language training; they educate (almost along the way) to better pronunciation and a feeling for the rhythm of the language. Reciting a poem in front of a crowd is no small feat. However, stage fright disappears once the first words have been spoken. Afterwards there is great joy. Of course, giving a presentation needs practice. It is important to speak clearly: the listeners should also understand what is at stake! We don't even let lazy mouths or bad articulation develop. Younger pupils are usually enthusiastic about family history. Interest is quickly aroused when they are asked to bring an old poetry album from their grandmother or great-grandmother. Old poetry albums have a special charm because they contain handwritten poems and wishes. The children and young people find a first approach to lyrical texts and see that they don't have to be boring.

One possibility for older pupils is to initially offer access to poetry via pictures. You can either take photos of these yourself / bring them with you or pictures will be offered on the selected subject area. This can be poems appropriate to the season or on topics such as nature, city poetry, change, future, etc. Teaching material on the subject of "nature" can be accessed on the state education server, and the ideas can also be transferred to other areas. In the classroom, too, rethinking is required. The purely analytical approach to poetry still dominates, and more attention must be paid to the creative approach to poetry, which is combined with analytical development, in order to win students over to poetry. The brevity of the lyrical texts, the semantic openness and ambiguity make them ideal for productive, action-oriented work.

One should also work with poems in German lessons. A fitting poem Finding it is a very challenging task. Below is a selected poem, along with assignments on the text.

In short, language games, songs and poems such as picture describing, storytelling and find difference have been used as teaching methods to improve learners' skills. The main aim of using games songs and poems is that anxiety and depression learners suffer from make it difficult to learn appropriately so that it helps to pupils make easier and more interesting than before. The implementation of games, songs and poems and other warm up activities succeeded in helping pupils to learn and to understand new vocabularies and they can easily learn by heart and remember for long period. When teacher use puzzles in teaching process, learners can enhance problem-solving skills and also critical thinking. Most of these pupils cope with using games, songs and poems methods as welcome from usual classroom and boring routine to enjoyable learning environment.

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